

Sclerophrys pantherina

Western Leopard Toad

Decoding
South Africa's
Biodiversity

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Group: Amphibian

Size: 115 to 147mm

Distribution:

This species is restricted to a narrow coastal strip from the Cape Peninsula to Agulhas National Park, with intermediate populations now locally extinct.

Importance:

The Western Leopard Toad is a narrow endemic of the Western Cape, South Africa, with several populations already lost. The remaining few are critical to the species' survival. Although it has shown some adaptability to urban and agricultural landscapes, it persists only in these heavily modified areas. Growing threats in these environments place the remaining, genetically distinct, populations at high risk of extinction.

PromethiON Sequencing Report:

Output: 135.64 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 3.53 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Genome Length: 3.6 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 86.7% [Single: 86.3%, Duplicated: 0.4%]

Assembly N50: 81.63 kilobases

Contig number: 110 518

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